

List of Public Docs

A personal collection of examples of *public docs* – online documents as publicly shared resources or micro-platforms for knowledge sharing, publishing, teaching, activism and more.

The selection is very much informed by the examples I'm exposed to in my own professional circles. A more systematic examination of the space would be worthwhile.

It would also be interesting to get a more taxonomic view on the range of forms these kind of documents take or could take – in terms of aesthetics and how they perform (what they do) in certain contexts; in terms of the organization of contributions and cooperative aspects; in terms of how the capabilities of the platforms are used or exploited in interesting ways, and so on.

For many more examples, I recommend the Are.na channel by Corey Tegeler:

[Radical Google Docs](#)

Sharing Knowledge, Resources, Directories

[Teaching-Design-ONLINE](#)

Google Docs

[Teaching-Design-Bibliography](#)

Google Sheets

[Decolonizing Reader](#)

Google Docs

[Decentering Whiteness in Design History Resources](#)

Google Docs

[Anti-Racism Design Resources](#)

Google Docs

[L.i.P. Collective list of archives and online resources](#)

Google Sheets

[Printers for #BlackLivesMatter](#)

Google Sheets

[Black Type Designers & Foundry Owners](#)

Notion

[Cyberfeminist Index \(~1990s-present\)](#)

Google Sheets

[A Collective Booklet for Computational Women](#)

Google Sheets

[Computing History Hub](#)

Notion

[Critical Data Center Studies](#)

Google Docs

[NEW MEDIA TOOLS](#)

Google Docs

[Open source, experimental, and tiny tools roundup](#)

GitHub

<https://tinytools.directory>

Google Sheets

[Ideas for teaching clay online](#)

Google Docs

[Teaching in the context of COVID-19](#)

Google Docs

[Resources for Online Instruction // VISUAL+STUDIO Arts Courses](#)

Google Docs

[Design Interns Club](#)

Google Sheets

[The Big Artist Opportunities List](#)

Google Sheets

[Postgrad Application Library](#)

Google Drive

<https://www.covidfaq.co>

Notion

Teaching, Workshops, Course Platforms

Evening Class

Google Sheets

Personal, Project & Portfolio Websites

Institutions as a Way of Life project

Google Docs

do does this (Website of design researcher Donato Ricci)

Google Docs

Experimental & Playful Formats

Party in a Shared Google Doc

Google Sheets

- Party in a Shared Google Doc (Article by Marie Foulston)